

Keywords:

#Multidisciplinary, #ClimateNeutral, #SmartCities, #SSHOC, #ENVRIFAIR, #ResearchCommunity, #EOSCinPractice

Advancing Multi-disciplinary Research through Cross-Domain Integration and Collaboration

Enhancing Multi-disciplinary Research through Cross-Domain Integration and Collaboration

The Project Involved

EOSC Future Science Project 9, "Climate Neutral and Smart Cities" (H2020 Grant Agreement 101017536), focuses on multi-disciplinary research through collaboration between the SSHOC cluster and ENVRIFAIR. Many experts and institutions are participating, including climate and air-quality scientists from the Swedish National Data Service, IAGOS, the Norwegian Center for Climate Service, and NILU, as well as experts on social survey data from the European Social Survey ERIC and CESSDA ERIC.

The User Community

This project has two main user communities: researchers engaged in multi-disciplinary projects and institutions dedicated to providing integrateable data effectively, both at scientific and technical levels.

The Challenge

Multiple levels of interoperability are considered, encompassing organizations, researchers, and required data resources and systems. The project supports collaborative research by integrating survey data from the European Social Survey, climate data from Copernicus, and air quality data from the European Environmental Agency.

Hilde Orten

Norwegian Agency for Shared Services in Education and Research, Bergen, Norway

"By involving experts from the different partner organizations, and adopting standards aimed at cross-domain FAIR implementation, we can provide the additional visibility into the integration methods and processes to effectively address relevant multi-disciplinary research questions."

This research examines environmental factors and their impact on urban inhabitants in various European cities, necessitating expertise across domains, access to diverse data sources, and agreement on semantics and technical implementation. The collaboration process is explored, and information needs of participants are identified. The project emphasizes establishing methods for data integration, from researchers to implementation and documentation, which includes developing a prototype system to support the use of integrated data.

The solution

By involving experts from different partner organizations and adopting standards aimed at cross-domain FAIR implementation, the project aims to enhance visibility into integration methods and processes, effectively addressing multi-disciplinary research questions. Cross-domain data use requires contextualizing metadata, providing a detailed description of data processing from its source form to an integrateable format suitable for researchers.

The provenance description is made accessible to researchers through an integrated browser view, based on the process description capabilities of the DDI - Cross-Domain Integration (DDI-CDI) standard. By providing visibility into data processing at each stage and linking it to descriptions of variables and methods (including the processing code), a better understanding of the resulting integrateable data can be presented. ESS Labs serves as the platform for showcasing these findings.

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Useful tips & tricks

Although the project already had an existing help desk system, efforts were made to integrate it with the EOSC Help Desk service. This integration was facilitated through meetings with professional and competent service providers, who explained the available options and assisted in selecting the appropriate one.

Benefits and impact

Society's complex challenges demand collaboration among researchers from various disciplines. The project highlights urban areas as examples, where understanding environmental and physical factors and their interactions with inhabitants' behaviors and attitudes is crucial. Organizational and scientific collaborations across domain boundaries can foster more creative and well-informed policies. The project aims to identify practical ways to enable such collaborations at all levels, from organizational and scientific to technical aspects. By exploring best practices in these areas, the project aims to contribute to the resulting societal benefits.

Why do I need EOSC?

Currently, there is no standard organizational framework for conducting multi-disciplinary research. EOSC offers a structure that facilitates interoperability and collaboration at all levels, becoming an integral part of the work of infrastructure players, data providers, technical implementers, and researchers. Without a framework like EOSC, such collaborations remain ad-hoc and cannot become regular scientific practice.

Across disciplines

The project's inherent focus is on cross-disciplinary science. Through the ESS Labs service, all project findings, including scientific collaboration, methods, data, implementation, metadata models, and programming code, are accessible to serve as an example of how to practically approach multi-disciplinary science.

Useful material related to this story

[climate-neutral-and-smart-cities_en](#)

[sshopencloud.eu](#)

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Future developments

The ESS Labs service envisions adding other prototypes and exemplary projects in the future, involving innovative approaches to social science data and its cross-domain use. Expanding beyond the current environmental and climate data projects, the ESS Labs approach provides a valuable channel for exploring future opportunities in various domains.

Future funding model scenarios

The ESS Labs service serves as a channel to expose further project results, combining reports and documentation with prototype implementations and supporting programming code and data. Future projects must identify their own funding sources and be relevant to the work of the ESS ERIC. Projects of all sizes will be considered based on topic complexity, the number of partners involved, and the degree of implementation, as long as the ESS remains a significant partner and supports the proposed additions to the ESS Labs in line with their current direction.

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